

Highly Sensitive Urea Sensor Based on Citric acid Capped plasmonic Copper quantum dots

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Abstract

Metallic quantum dots have received greater attention due to their wide applications as a colorimetric sensor due to their high sensitivity and easy device integration. Herein, we report a one step method to synthesis metallic copper (CuQDs) quantum dots using citric acid and Sodium Borohydride (NaBH₄) as capping and reducing agent, respectively. As prepared CuQDs solution appears light bluish green color due to the Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR). The color of the CuQDs adsorbed cotton plug changed from light green to dark blue in the presence of Urea. The proposed method can find extensive applications in clinical sensors and also for detecting urea in water samples in high fidelity.

Keywords: Copper Nanoparticles, Surface Plasmon Resonance, Urea.

References

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